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Session 89 - Reflexivity and the Self in Institutional Ethnography

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Title: *Vulnerable Selves?* Coinvestigating lone mothers experiences with a reflexive and dialogic approach

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This paper draws on data from the first fieldwork of an Institutional Ethnography (IE) project that the author is conducting in four European countries. Through the description of the emersion – during the fieldwork – of the institutional processes that define and shape the single mothers' understanding of their *vulnerabilities*, this paper aims to contribute to the theoretical and methodological discussion on the process of reflexive understanding in IE.

The research study took into consideration – Study on TRansition and Exclusion in Society of Single-Mums (STRESS-Mums) – has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no 843976. The study collects data in three EU countries (Belgium, Italy and Spain) and in the UK, with discursive interviews to lone mothers, professionals (judges, lawyers, other experts) and gender issues activists, participant observations, document analysis and photo-voice sessions with the mothers and the professionals.

The study explores the lone mothers' manifest and hidden 'work' of legitimation and of possible de-legitimation by institutions, analyzing the *transition* from double parenthood to lone motherhood, that is the

period of judicial evaluation for child custody and judicial decisions for children/family allowances and divorce/separation. Attention to that transition was addressed since, according to some authors, the laws on the shared custody of children seem to conceal, in their reference to parents' equality, new forms of male dominance embodied in the cultural paradigms of Western societies. In other words, a sort of naturalization of dominance relations maybe not very visible and recognized in this law.

Analyzing the in-depth interviews conducted with single mothers during the first fieldwork of this IE project, this paper highlights how the Self of the ethnographer and the Selves of the participants co-investigate the single mothers' experiences in a way that generates trust, awareness and reflexive rethinking of some issues.

According to Smith (2006), co-investigation is made possible by a reflexive dialogue between the ethnographer's Self and the participants' Selves. The dialogic approach (or style) the author utilizes in creating the interview guide and in interviewing these single mothers results from the theoretical suggestions of Martin Buber (1937) about the relationships with the Otherness, Michail Bakhtin (1981) about the dialogic use of the empathy and 'exotopy' or 'exotopia' (a word from the ancient Greek language that means 'extra-localization' or collocation outside our presupposed meanings) in communicating with the Otherness, and other authors from the field of symbolic interactionism (La Mendola 2009) about the co-construction of the ethnographer and participants' awareness. This dialogic approach, applied to the interviewing process, contributed to a co-construction of knowledge (i.e., constructing knowledge together) with the interviewee, in creating a reflexive coinvestigation. In addition, this approach facilitates processes of comfortable self-disclosure and self-discovery, without threatening the boundaries of the participant's Self.

The utilization of this style is exemplified and discussed through audio and video-recorded fragments from the interviews, that make possible looking at the embodied experience of the relations between the Self of the interviewer and the Self of the interviewees and at the process of 'understanding together'. Furthermore, fragments from the ethnographer's journal concerning her own, intimate dialogue on her vulnerabilities (inside and outside the fieldwork) allow this presentation to describe and to discuss the process of understanding the participants' vulnerabilities.

In conclusion, the process of investigating the single mothers' experiences and vulnerabilities in this IE project, allows understanding the 'work' of the participants' Selves in assuming, resisting, and negotiating with the ruling perspectives of the institutions.

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